

A multifrequency image reconstruction for electrical impedance tomography to retain tissue spectral information

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Abstract: Electrical Impedance Tomography (EIT) is a medical imaging technique used to monitor patient respiration. It's safe, non-invasive, and cost-effective but suffers from low spatial resolution and poor tissue discrimination due to its reliance on single-frequency alternating current measurements. We present a new EIT reconstruction algorithm that uses multi-frequency measurements to account for the spectral properties of tissues. Tested on a simulated phantom with muscle and lung tissue data, this algorithm retains frequency dependence, improving tissue distinguishability in EIT images.

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I. Introduction

Electrical Impedance Tomography (EIT) is a medical imaging technique based on electrical measurements. It uses electrodes to inject small alternating currents and record the resulting voltages. Commonly used at the bedside, EIT monitors patient ventilation via an electrode belt around the thorax. From the measured voltages, the conductivity distribution of the chest is reconstructed by using the EIT reconstruction algorithm. This involves solving an inverse problem using a forward model, which is the mathematical formulation of the measurements. However, due to the intrinsic nonlinear nature of the forward model and the reliance on peripheral measurements, the inverse problem is severely ill-posed, where a stable solution is not directly possible, resulting in low spatial resolution in EIT images.

However, it is possible to use alternating currents at more than one frequency, which is known as multifrequency EIT or *mfEIT* and several authors took advantage of multifrequency measurements incorporating this feature in the EIT reconstruction [1], [2], [3], [4].

In this contribution, we introduce a new multifrequency reconstruction method based on a modified forward model restricted to spatial functions where frequency dependence is introduced via a tensor product with a frequency function. This restricts EIT inverse problem solutions to those satisfying the proposed tensor product, correlating spatial and spectral information. The main advantage of this approach is its simplicity, allowing the use of established EIT tools like regularization strategies and forward problem frameworks. Additionally, the components of the tensor product can be easily exchanged, enhancing flexibility.

II. Material and methods

To validate the proposed EIT reconstruction algorithm, we used the Matlab package EIDORS version 3.11 [5]. We simulated two 2D disk phantoms with 16 electrodes using the Finite Element Method (FEM). Conductivities for muscle and inflated/deflated lung tissues were interpolated from the literature [6], [7] between 100 kHz and 1 MHz to mimic multifrequency EIT acquisition.

The first phantom, entirely muscle tissue, served as a reference, while the second included deflated and inflated lung tissue targets (see Fig. 1 a).

The tensor product included up to the 20th radial order of Zernike polynomials for spatial functions and a third-order polynomial for the frequency correlation. This resulted in 924 degrees of freedom compared to 3136 for traditional EIT methods which is the number of the elements in the FEM. Conductance variations were reconstructed using raw data, comparing standard EIT approaches with Tikhonov regularization and frequency correlation. Different FEM meshes were used for the forward and inverse models, with 0.1% white noise added to the simulations.

For reproducibility, the complete code is available in a public repository (https://bit.ly/BMT2024_github), whereas the reference implementation together with the mathematical formulation is available elsewhere [8].

III. Results and discussion

Fig. 1 a) shows the simulation ground truth while the frequency-correlated reconstructed images at several frequencies are displayed in Fig. 1 b) to h) with a normalized colormap.

Figure 1: Simulated phantom and reconstruction results. a) Simulated phantom with highlighted three points belonging to target 1 (left, deflated lung), target 2 (right, inflated lung), and the background (bottom, muscle). Image reconstruction at b) 100 kHz, c) 150 kHz, d) 220 kHz, e) 320 kHz, f) 460 kHz, g) 680 kHz, and h) 1 MHz. Colors are normalized to the same scale.

These images are very similar to those obtained with the standard method (not shown here) and show well-defined dark blue area of low conductivity at the position of target 2 and a less defined light blue area at the target 1 location, while the rest of the images show yellow artifacts on a white background.

The ground truth conductivity difference for the three points highlighted in Fig. 1 a) taken against the reference simulation are shown in Fig. 2 alongside the conductivity difference recovered from the multifrequency reconstruction.

Confronting Fig. 2 a) with b) it is evident that the multifrequency reconstruction method preserved the frequency trend of the tissue as well as the difference values. This proves that the proposed multifrequency EIT algorithm outperformed the standard one regarding frequency trends. However, there are limitations. First, the work is based on a well-defined simulation, and further verification is needed with a larger dataset. Second, the phantom's geometry favored the use of Zernike functions. Despite this, the algorithm only requires perturbations in the form of a tensor product, allowing for easy adaptation to other basis functions. Additionally, while the spectral

Figure 2: Differential tissue conductance. a) Reconstructed data for the three points of Fig. 1 a). Data from the literature [6], [7].

dependence was chosen simply, it can incorporate more complex prior information.

IV. Conclusions

The proposed EIT reconstruction algorithm, which enforces frequency correlation, successfully produced images resembling the simulated ground truth at all frequencies. These images were similar to those from a standard EIT algorithm. However, while both methods distinguished the simulated targets, only the frequency correlation approach retained the quantitative trend of tissue conductivity, improving tissue distinguishability in EIT images.

AUTHOR'S STATEMENT

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